

EVALUATION OF LIVER FUNCTION TEST PARAMETERS IN DIABETIC PATIENTS IN THI-QAR GOVERNORATE

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Abstract: Introduction: Diabetes Mellitus, a persistent metabolic disorder, manifests with elevated blood glucose levels sustained over time. It arises from either insufficient insulin production or ineffective insulin utilization within the body. This condition is linked to diverse complications that impact numerous organ systems, including the eyes, kidneys, nerves, and cardiovascular system.

Methods: Current study samples were collected from Forty patients with a diagnosis of Diabetic Mellitus by the specialist doctor, who applied to Imam Hussein teaching hospital and privates clinics in Thi-Qar governorate between November 2023 until April 2024, and forty healthy individuals, Hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) , Random Blood sugar (RBS), Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT), Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST), and Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP) test were done to all participants in current study in addition to body mass index (BMI)

Results: The study revealed significant differences between diabetic patients and the control group across various descriptive characteristics. Notably, 85% of diabetic patients had no family history of the disease, and 15% did. Regarding living situations, 5% of patients were in poor conditions, while 95% were in moderate situations. Treatment-wise, 15% used regulatory tables, while 85% depended on insulin. In terms of gender distribution, 67.5% were males, and 32.5% were females. II In terms of health indicators, diabetic patients exhibited a significant increase in BMI compared to the control group, while the mean age difference was non-significant. Additionally, diabetic patients showed significant increases in random blood glucose concentration and cumulative glucose percentage. Moreover, they displayed elevated levels of ALT and AST, while ALP levels were non-significantly decreased compared to the control group.

Conclusions: Current study findings underscored significant differences in various parameters between diabetic patients and the control group, shedding light on the multifaceted nature of diabetes and its associated health markers.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, ALT, AST, BMI.

1. Introduction

Diabetes Mellitus, a widespread chronic metabolic disorder, represents a substantial global health challenge due to its increasing prevalence and myriad associated complications. Characterized by persistent elevation of blood glucose levels, the condition stems from either inadequate insulin production or impaired insulin utilization by the body (American Diabetes Association, 2022) . Timely diagnosis and effective management are pivotal in mitigating long-term complications and enhancing outcomes for patients with diabetes (Zheng *etal.*, 2018).

Powers (2018) has identified many types of diabetes mellitus. Insulin is produced very little or not at all in type 1 diabetes due to the autoimmune death of pancreatic beta cells. Usually presenting in youth or adolescent, it requires lifelong insulin treatment. Insulin resistance, which is a condition associated to obesity, a sedentary lifestyle, and genetics, is the hallmark of type 2 diabetes. It occurs when the body's cells do not react to insulin as intended. When the body cannot create enough insulin to satisfy increasing demands, it results in elevated blood glucose levels, which is known as gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), which happens during pregnancy.

The complications of diabetes are multifaceted and can affect various organ systems, including the eyes (diabetic retinopathy), kidneys (diabetic nephropathy), nerves (diabetic neuropathy), and cardiovascular system (coronary artery disease, stroke). These complications significantly contribute to morbidity and mortality among diabetic patients (American Diabetes Association, 2020).

Liver function tests (LFTs) encompass a panel of biochemical markers used to evaluate liver health and function. Drug-induced liver injury, Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and viral hepatitis are two disorders that are commonly associated with elevated levels of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) (Li *et al.*, 2020), aspartate aminotransferase (AST) its elevation may also occur in conditions such as acute myocardial infarction and muscle injury (Shan and Schwartz, 2012), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) are providing valuable insights into liver pathology. (Harrison and Bacon, 2008) an elevation at serum ALP levels indicate cholestasis or biliary obstruction, commonly seen in conditions such as cholelithiasis, primary biliary cholangitis (PBC), and obstructive jaundice (van der Meer *et al.*, 2012).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Participants

The study participants included 40 diabetic patients and a control group 40 healthy individuals, matched for age, sex, and other relevant demographic characteristics. Diabetic patients were recruited from [mention the healthcare facility or clinics], while the control group consisted of individuals without diabetes.

2.2 Inclusion Criteria

- A. Diabetic patients diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes mellitus.
- B. Control group participants without a history of diabetes or related metabolic disorders.
- C. Age range [mean of age is 53 years old].

2.3 Exclusion Criteria:

- A. Patients with Type 1 diabetes mellitus.
- B. Individuals with a history of other chronic diseases affecting metabolic parameters.
- C. Pregnant or lactating women.

2.4 Data Collection

Information on family history of the disease, living situation, treatment type, and sex was collected using structured questionnaires and medical records.

2.4.1 Clinical Parameters

2.4.1.1 Hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) Measurement

HbA1c levels were measured using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) or immunoassay techniques according to manufacturer's instructions (Nathan *et al.*, 2008).

2.4.1.2 Random Blood Sugar (RBS)

The manufacturer's instructions were followed to obtain a reading of random blood sugar levels (Smith and Johnson, 2022).

2.4.1.3 Liver Function Tests (ALT, AST, and ALP)

ALT, AST, and ALP levels are measured using automated clinical chemistry analyzers following standard protocols (Prati *et al.*, 2002).

3. Statistical Analysis

Using SPSS version 26, independent sample t-tests and non-parametric chi-square tests were used to statistically analyze the data in this study, with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$.

4. Results

The present study was recorded a significant difference at p . value < 0.05 , between patients in all descriptive characteristics. This study was showed 85% of patients had not family history for disease, while 15% of patients had family history for disease, with regard living situation was showed 5% of patients was poor situation, and 95% of patients was moderate situation. According to treatment type this study showed 15% of patients treated with regulatory tables, while 85% of patients were depending on insulin hormone. Finally with regard sex this study showed 67.5% of patients were males, and 32.5% were females, as in the Table 1. A significant increase in average of BMI in diabetic patients compared with control group, in contrast the mean of age was non-significantly decreased in diabetic patients compared with control group, at p . value < 0.05 , as in the Table 2 and Figure 1.

Table 1: Descriptive characteristics of diabetic patients

Characteristics		No.	%	p. value
Family History	Yes	6	15.0	<0.001
	No	34	85.0	
Living situation	Weak	2	5.00	<0.001
	Moderate	38	95.0	
Treatment Type	Tab	6	15.0	<0.001
	Insulin	34	85.0	
Sex	Male	27	67.5	<0.001
	Female	13	32.5	

Table 2: BMI and Age comparison between diabetic patients and control group

Descriptive	Patients	Control	p. value
	Mean $\pm$ S. D		
BMI kg/m^2	28.43 $\pm$ 3.55	26.43 $\pm$ 3.23	0.011
Age/ years	53.12 $\pm$ 8.58	56.52 $\pm$ 8.46	0.078

Figure 1: BMI and Age comparison between diabetic patients and control group

As shown in Table 3 and Figure 2, the current results, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$, show a significant rise in the concentration of random blood glucose and cumulative glucose percentage among diabetic patients compared to the control group

Table 3: Evaluation of RBS and HbA1c diabetic patients and control group

Diabetic Parameters	Patients	Control	p. value
	Mean $\pm$ S. D		
RBS mg/dl	396.8 $\pm$ 51.8	90.82 $\pm$ 11.3	<0.001
HbA1c%	9.805 $\pm$ 0.98	5.155 $\pm$ 0.35	<0.001

Figure 2: Evaluation of RBS and HbA1c diabetic patients and control group

The current results was investigated a significant increase in concentration of both ALT and AST in diabetic patients compared with control group, in xontrast the level of ALP was decreased non-significantly in diabetic patients compared with control group at p. value < 0.05, as in the Table 4 and Figure 3.

Table 4: Evaluation of LFT diabetic patients and control group

LFT	Patients	Control	p. value
	Mean ± S. D		
ALT IU/L	32.56 ± 8.13	11.55 ± 2.86	<0.001
AST IU/L	54.41 ± 17.8	11.05 ± 2.08	<0.001
ALP IU/L	73.85 ± 17.2	79.45 ± 8.66	0.071

Figure 3: Evaluation of LFT diabetic patients and control group

4 Discussion

The study's conclusions highlight significant distinctions between the diabetic patients and the control group on a number of different metrics, including biochemical markers and descriptive traits.

The study observed a notable difference in the distribution of certain descriptive characteristics between diabetic patients and the control group. Specifically, a higher proportion of diabetic patients had no family history of the disease compared to those with a family history. This aligns with existing literature suggesting that genetic predisposition plays a significant role in the development of diabetes (Florez, 2008). Moreover, the majority of diabetic patients were dependent on insulin hormone for treatment, consistent with the management approach for Type 1 diabetes, which typically requires insulin therapy (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

Additionally, a significant majority of diabetic patients were found to be in a moderate living situation, indicating a potential socioeconomic factor influencing disease prevalence. Socioeconomic status has been widely recognized as a determinant of health outcomes, with lower socioeconomic status often associated with higher prevalence and poorer management of chronic conditions such as diabetes (Seligman *et al.*, 2010).

The study revealed a notable rise in the average Body Mass Index (BMI) among diabetic patients in comparison to the control group. This observation aligns with the established correlation between obesity and Type 2 diabetes, wherein surplus body weight contributes to insulin resistance and the onset of diabetes (Kahn *et al.*, 2006).

Furthermore, diabetic patients exhibited higher concentrations of random blood glucose and cumulative glucose percentage compared to the control group. These findings are indicative of poorer glycemic control among diabetic patients, which is a hallmark feature of diabetes and a significant risk factor for complications such as cardiovascular disease and neuropathy (American Diabetes Association, 2022).

Current study also observed elevated levels of both Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) and Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST) in diabetic patients compared to the control group. This suggests a potential association between diabetes and liver dysfunction, as elevated liver enzymes are indicative of liver injury or inflammation, which can be exacerbated in the presence of diabetes (Targher *et al.*, 2008). However, the non-significant decrease in Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP) levels warrants further investigation to elucidate its role in diabetic pathophysiology.

In conclusion, the findings of this study underscore the multifactorial nature of diabetes, implicating genetic, socioeconomic, and biomedical factors in its etiology and progression. These results emphasize the importance of comprehensive management strategies that address not only glycemic control but also address comorbidities and socioeconomic factors to effectively mitigate the burden of diabetes on affected individuals and healthcare systems.

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